

Terpenoids and Related Compounds. Part VIII'. *Acacia Pennata* Bark

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Lupeol and α -spinasterol have been isolated from the neutral fraction of the benzene extract of the bark of *Acacia pennata*. Physical properties suggest the identity of acaciol with α -spinasterol.

In recent years several plants of the genus *Acacia* (Fam. Leguminosæ) have been investigated and found to contain triterpene alcohols and acids. Gedeon² reported the isolation of a triterpene acid, $C_{30}H_{46}O_6$, from the fruit of *A. concina*. Later from the bark of *A. intisa* Farooq *et al.*³ isolated an acid genin and two neutral genins, of which one was identified as the triterpene alcohol, lupeol, and the other was reported to be an unknown alcohol. The acid genin, named acacic acid, found in other *Acacia* species⁴ also, has been investigated in detail and a structure for it has been suggested⁵.

The unknown neutral genin³, which was believed to be a new pentacyclic triterpene alcohol, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, was named acaciol by Farooq *et al.*⁶, who carried out several transformations on it, but could not arrive at any definite structure. Incidentally, Nigam *et al.*⁷ reported the isolation of stigmasterol and a triterpene alcohol, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 182°, besides an aliphatic hydroxy compound, $C_{21}H_{40}O_3$, m.p. 104°, from the bark of *A. caesia*.

The present authors have undertaken to study the bark of *Acacia pennata* which has not yet been examined chemically. *Acacia pennata* (Linn.) Willd. grows in Central and Eastern Himalayas, Oudh, W. Bengal, Bihar, and South India. The juice of the bark is used as an antidote for snake poison⁸. The benzene extract of the stem bark was separated into ethersoluble and ether-insoluble fractions. The former fraction was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction on chromatography over alumina first provided lupeol, identified as its acetate by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

The second solid to come out of the column on acetylation and crystallisation furnished a crystalline compound, m.p. 180-81°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, which on hydrolysis yielded an alcohol, m.p. 162-64°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. The alcohol on benzylation provided a benzoate, m.p. 104-97°, $[\alpha]_D +2.1^\circ$.

The physical properties of the alcohol, its acetate, and benzoate agree very satisfactorily with those of α -spinasterol, its acetate, and benzoate respectively (Table I).

1. Part VII, Sengupta and Mukhopadhyay . . . unpublished.

2. *Arch. Pharm.*, 1955, 288, 417.

3. *Ann. Pharm.*, 1959, 17, 442.

4. *Arch. Pharm.*, 1961, 294, 133; 1962, 295, 12.

5. Varshney and Shamsuddin, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, No. 17, 1187 and references cited therein.

6. *Arch. Pharm.*, 1961, 294, 197.

7. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 345.

8. Chopra, Nayar, and Chopra, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants', Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 2.

The alcohol shows positive Tortelli-Jaffe colour test⁹ which is specific for steroids having Δ^7 , Δ^8 or $\Delta^8(14)$ ethylenic linkages. Further, the IR spectra of the acetate show a peak at 978 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the absorption band¹⁰ for *transoid* ethylenic linkage, present in the side chain of α -spinasterol.

It seems very likely that *acoaiol* of Farooq *et al.*⁸ is in fact α -spinasterol and not a pentacyclic triterpene alcohol, as is evident from a comparison of the physical properties of *acoaiol** and its derivatives with those of α -spinasterol and its derivatives (Table I).

TABLE I

	<i>Acoaiol.</i>		α -Spinasterol. (Present authors).		(Lit. ¹¹).	
	M.P.	$[\alpha]_D$.	M.P.	$[\alpha]_D$.	M.P.	$[\alpha]_D$.
Alcohol	.. 180-81,	± 0	162-04°,	$\pm 0^\circ$	172-78°	-3.7°
Acetate	174-75°,	$\pm 0^\circ$	180-81°,		187°,	-4.7°
Benzoate		..	194-97°,	$\pm 2.1^\circ$	201-202°	+2.26°
Ketone	.. 170-71°	..	..	..	176° ¹²	

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried and powdered bark (3.6 kg.) of *A. pennata* was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet for 8 hr. The resinous mass (18 g.), obtained after removal of benzene, was taken in ether and filtered from some amorphous solid which resisted all attempts at crystallisation. The ether solution was shaken with a cold 10% aqueous NaOH solution and then with water. It was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish a yellow viscous gum (15 g.).

Lupeol Acetate.—The above neutral gummy material was chromatographed over activated alumina (300 g.). After a forerun of an oily material (4.83 g.), elution with a mixture of light petroleum and benzene (2:3) furnished a partially crystalline solid (0.65 g.) which on digestion with methanol provided a crystalline solid (0.5 g.). The solid was acetylated in the usual manner with acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (5 ml). The crude acetate on several crystallisations from a mixture of methanol and acetone yielded lupeol acetate (0.07 g.), m.p. $213-14^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D +38^\circ$, which did not depress the melting point of an authentic specimen. It exhibited a single spot in thin-layer chromatography and showed positive test with tetranitromethane. (Found: C, 81.93; H, 11.16. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.00; H, 11.18%).

α -*Spinasterol Acetate.*—Elution with a mixture of light petroleum and benzene (1:4) in the above chromatogram furnished a partially crystalline solid (0.75 g.) which was rechromatographed over activated alumina (150 g.). Elution with the same solvent mixture

* A direct comparison could not be made since we failed to procure a sample of *acoaiol*.

9. Fieser and Fieser, "Natural Products Related to Phenanthrene", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1949, p. 101.

10. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1960, p. 34.

11. Hallbron, Bunbury, Cook and Jones, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. 4, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, p. 889.

12. Simpson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 730.

furnished a colorless crystalline material (0.5 g.), m.p. 150-56°, which was acetylated in the usual manner with acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (5 ml). The crude acetate crystallising from the reaction medium on several crystallisations from acetone yielded pure α -spinasterol acetate (0.06 g.), m.p. 180-81°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. It showed a single spot in TLC and positive test with tetranitromethane. (Found: C, 82.03; H, 11.18. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.88; H, 11.08%). IR peaks at 1720 and 1210 cm^{-1} (acetate), and 978 cm^{-1} (transoid $-\text{CH} = \text{CH}-$).

α -*Spinasterol*.—The above acetate (0.1 g.) was refluxed for 2 hr. with 10% methanolic KOH (5 ml) and benzene (4 ml). After working up as usual, the crude solid was crystallised from methanol to furnish α -spinasterol (0.09 g.), m.p. 162-64°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. It showed a single spot in TLC and positive reactions with tetranitromethane and the Tollens-Jaffe reagent. IR peak at 3650 cm^{-1} (non-bonded OH).

α -*Spinasterol Benzoate*.— α -Spinasterol (0.08 g.) was benzoylated in the usual manner with benzoyl chloride (1.6 ml) and pyridine (8 ml). The crude benzoate on several crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished pure α -spinasterol benzoate, m.p. 94-197°, $[\alpha]_D +2.1^\circ$.

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